

Proposed changes to the masonry chapter in EC8 Part 1

Background document for the masonry chapter in EC8 Part 1

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Version: 14.03.2021

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3776777

Link to document on Zenodo.org: <https://zenodo.org/record/3776777>

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1 Objective of this document

This document summarises the background for changes proposed in the masonry chapter of EC8 – Part 1-2 with regard to the current version of EC8 – Part 1 [1]. Note that separate

background documents exist for drift capacities of URM walls, behaviour factors and slenderness limits and the design of simple buildings.

2 Materials and bonding patterns

2.1 Robustness of masonry units

2004	9.2.1(1)	<p>9.2.1 Types of masonry units</p> <p>(1) Masonry units should have sufficient robustness in order to avoid local brittle failure.</p> <p>NOTE The National Annex may select the type of masonry units from EN 1996-1:2004, Table 3.1 that satisfy (1).</p>
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Tomazevic and co-workers [2], [3] investigated whether the strength of hollow clay masonry units has an influence on the robustness of masonry walls. In their work, robustness is mainly linked to the hysteretic energy dissipation. The authors found that the hysteretic energy dissipation is mainly affected by the axial load ratio and recommend to limit this ratio to 0.15-0.20. They explicitly state that no other requirements to characterise robustness are necessary. The ratio of horizontal to vertical brick compressive strength of the units that were included in their study was $f_{bh}/f_b \geq 0.23$.

Another experimental study that investigated the influence of two different hollow clay masonry units are the quasi-static cyclic tests on composite spandrels (URM spandrel + RC beam) by Beyer and Dazio [4]. In this study, spandrels with two types of units were tested. The spandrel tests where units with a ratio of $f_{bh}/f_b = 0.14$ were used, featured the formation of vertical crushing bands relatively early on in the test. The spandrel tests where units with a ratio of $f_{bh}/f_b = 0.29$ were used did not develop such crushing bands.

Shear force capacity models for in-plane loaded URM walls that are based on the lower bound theorem of plasticity were developed by Ganz and Thürlimann (e.g. [5], [6]) and continued by Mojsilovic [7], [8]. These models show that the shear strength of URM walls depends on the vertical compressive strength and the horizontal compressive strength of the masonry. According to these models, the load bearing mechanism can be represented by vertical and inclined stress fields. A lower bound estimate of the capacity of the inclined stress field is the horizontal compressive strength of the masonry. According to EC6, 5.6.1.4 (2) [9], the masonry compressive strength parallel to the bed joint can be computed from the "(...) normalized compressive strength of the masonry unit, f_b , obtained from tests where the direction of application of the load to the test specimen is the same as the direction of the action effect in the masonry (...)".

This shows that the horizontal strength of units has an effect on the shear strength of the masonry. Masonry typologies that lead to a large ratio of vertical compressive strength to horizontal compressive strength may favour crushing in the horizontal direction when subjected to shear-compression loading. However, detailed guidelines on determining the unit strength parallel to the bed joints seem to be missing (e.g. how to prepare specimens from units with tongue and groove), which renders the application of EC6 difficult.

Based on the observations from these two experimental studies the following changes are recommended:

- Robustness should be characterised by the ratio of horizontal to vertical brick compressive strength and the axial load ratio (ALR).
- Because for walls subjected to shear-compression loading, the failure of the inclined compression strut is not checked explicitly in EC6, it is suggested to

introduce a lower limit of f_{bh}/f_b . Based on the available experimental evidence, it is suggested to limit the ratio of horizontal to vertical brick strength f_{bh}/f_b to 0.15. However, such a limit should only be introduced if clear guidelines with regard to the testing of f_{bh} are provided in EN 772-1.

- The effect of the ALR on the deformation capacity is accounted for through an ALR limit for the masonry walls. The effect of the ALR on the deformation capacity on URM walls is analysed in the background document on drift capacities of modern masonry walls [10].
- Future work: Robustness should best be characterised as ratio of drift capacity at axial load failure to the ultimate drift capacity. Unfortunately only very few test campaigns very continued up to axial load failure.

2.2 Minimum strength of masonry units and minimum strength of mortar

2004	9.2.2(1)	<p>9.2.2 Minimum strength of masonry units</p> <p>(1) Except in cases of low seismicity, the normalised compressive strength of masonry units, derived in accordance with EN 772-1, should be not less than the minimum values as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – normal to the bed face: $f_{b,min}$. – parallel to the bed face in the plane of the wall: $f_{bh,min}$. <p>NOTE The values ascribed to $f_{b,min}$ and $f_{bh,min}$ for use in a country may be found in its National Annex of this document. The recommended values are $f_{b,min} = 5 \text{ N/mm}^2$ $f_{bh,min} = 2 \text{ N/mm}^2$.</p>
2004	9.2.3(1)	<p>9.2.3 Mortar</p> <p>(1) A minimum strength is required for mortar, $f_{m,min}$, which generally exceeds the minimum specified in EN 1996.</p> <p>NOTE The value ascribed to $f_{m,min}$ for use in a country may be found in its National Annex of this document. The recommended value is $f_{m,min} = 5 \text{ N/mm}^2$ for unreinforced or confined masonry and $f_{m,min} = 10 \text{ N/mm}^2$ for reinforced masonry.</p>

Figure 1 shows the drift capacity as a function of the unit strength and the mortar strength. For all three failure modes, the drift capacity seems independent of the unit strength while a lower mortar strength leads to higher drift capacities than a higher mortar strength. Low strength mortar seems therefore to be beneficial for the deformation capacity of the walls. However, above mortar strengths of 5 MPa, the influence is not very strong and has not been considered in the drift capacity models suggested in [10].

Based on the experimental results available [2], [3], [10], the brick and mortar strength does not need to be considered explicitly but it is sufficient to limit the ALR of the masonry wall in order to reach a robust behaviour of the URM wall under quasi-static cyclic loading. However, for unreinforced masonry, minimum strength requirements on units and mortar can be seen as a second line of defense. Furthermore, as the applied drift capacity models are empirical, the applicability should be limited to mortar and brick strengths that have been sufficiently well investigated.

It is therefore suggested to maintain the limit on the brick strength but this limit cannot be derived based on first principles. It could be related to available data In the database, 14 out of the 135 tests have brick strengths lower than 4 MPa and this could serve as an indicator for a lower limit on the unit strength. It is further suggested to remove the mortar strength limit for unreinforced masonry. Instead, a limit on the ALR will be introduced because there is ample evidence that it has a significant influence on the response of URM walls.

For reinforced masonry, the mortar quality also influences the bond between rebars and mortar. Mortar strength requirements in EC6 [9] are part of national annexes while EC6 prescribes a minimum characteristic compressive strength of 20 MPa for concrete infills (Section 5.3.2(1)). For the reinforced masonry, 10 MPa as proposed in the current version of EC8 is adopted.

Note: The removal of the strength related Nationally Determined Parameters (NDPs) disagrees with the approach taken in the revision of EC6 [9] (e.g. shear strength in Section 5.6.2).

Figure 1: European database of URM wall tests: Drift capacity as a function of the unit strength (a) and the mortar strength (b).

File register:

fig_brick_and_mortar_strength_1.m	Figure 1
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2.3 Masonry bond

2004	9.2.4(1)	<p>9.2.4 Masonry bond</p> <p>(1) There are three alternative classes of perpend joints:</p> <p>a) joints fully grouted with mortar;</p> <p>b) ungrouted joints;</p> <p>c) ungrouted joints with mechanical interlocking between masonry units.</p> <p>NOTE The National Annex may specify which ones among the three classes above will be allowed to be used in a country or parts of the country.</p>
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The data available on the drift capacity of unreinforced masonry does not allow concluding on the influence of the perpend joint on the drift capacity [10]. For this reason, it is suggested to remove this clause. However, all the available tests (with the exception of stone masonry wall tests) investigated walls where the units of two consecutive rows overlapped by half the unit length. For this reason, it is suggested to include this requirement here. The limits introduced in EC6 [9], Section 10.1.4 require less overlap.

Note that the class of perpend joint has a significant effect on the shear stiffness of the masonry element. For walls with ungrouted perpend joint, the shear stiffness is lower than for walls with fully grouted perpend joint.

3 Types of construction and behaviour factors

3.1 Ductility classes of masonry buildings

2004		Nothing
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Section 4.4.2(3) in EC8-Part 1 [11]:

(3) Regarding their deformation capacity and cumulative energy dissipation capacity, structures should be categorised in three ductility classes: DC1 (Ductility Class 1), DC2 (Ductility Class 2) and DC3 (Ductility Class 3).

NOTE 1 In DC1, the overstrength capacity is taken into account, while the deformation capacity and energy dissipation capacity are disregarded by EN1998 methods of analysis.

NOTE 2 In DC2, the local overstrength capacity, the local deformation capacity and the local energy dissipation capacity are taken into account by EN1998 methods of analysis. [There are no requirements for verification of the ability of the structure to form a global plastic mechanism at SD limit state]

NOTE 3 In DC3, the ability of the structure to form a global plastic mechanism at SD limit state and its local overstrength capacity, local deformation capacity and local energy dissipation capacity are taken into account by EN1998 methods of analysis.

3.2 Types of construction

2004	9.3.	<p>(2) Due to its low tensile strength and low ductility, unreinforced masonry that follows the provisions of EN 1996 alone is considered to offer low-dissipation capacity (DCL) and its use should be limited, provided that the effective thickness of walls, t_{ef}, is not less than a minimum value, $t_{ef,min}$.</p> <p>NOTE 1 The conditions under which unreinforced masonry that follows the provisions of EN 1996 alone may be used in a country, may be found in its National Annex to this document. Such use is recommended only in low seismicity cases (see 3.2.1(4)).</p> <p>NOTE 2 The value ascribed to $t_{ef,min}$ for use in a country of unreinforced masonry that follows the provisions of EN 1996 alone, may be found in its National Annex of this document. The recommended values of $t_{ef,min}$ are those in the 2nd column, 2nd and 3rd rows of Table 9.2.</p> <p>(3) For the reasons noted in (2) of this subclause, unreinforced masonry satisfying the provisions of the present Eurocode may not be used if the value of $a_{g,S}$, exceeds a certain limit, $a_{g,urm}$.</p> <p>NOTE The value ascribed to $a_{g,urm}$ for use in a country may be found in its National Annex of this document. This value should not be less than that corresponding to the threshold for the low seismicity cases. The value ascribed to $a_{g,urm}$ should be consistent with the values adopted for the minimum strength of masonry units, $f_{b,min}$, $f_{bh,min}$ and of mortar, $f_{m,min}$. For the values recommended in the Notes to 9.2.2 and 9.2.3, the recommended value of $a_{g,urm}$ is 0,20 g.</p>
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It is suggested to delete both clauses. Unreinforced masonry buildings should be designed according to the principles in EC8 and not be outruled when they pass all design checks.

3.3 Behaviour factors

The behaviour factors are treated in a separate background document.

4 Structural analysis

4.1 Shear stiffness of masonry piers

The final draft of EC6 [9] suggests as the current version of EC6 [14] that the shear modulus G may be estimated as 40% of the elastic modulus E (Section 5.7.3(1), [9]).

Wilding and Beyer [12] report that the American code ASCE 41 [15] refers for the G/E ratio to TMS 402, which concludes that the ratio of 0.4 has no experimental basis [16]. From experimental results, it was found that the G/E -ratio can be significantly lower than 0.4. Tomazevic [17] proposes to use a G/E -ratio of 0.1; Petry and Beyer [18] and Wilding and Beyer [19] assume a G/E -ratio of 0.25. Ongoing analytical work by Wilding et al. [20] on the elastic composite material shows that this ratio depends largely on the mortar-to-brick elastic modulus ratio, the joint-to-brick height ratio and the mortar Poisson's ratio. For typical masonry configurations it varies between 0.2 and 0.4.

To summarise: The G/E -ratio is a matter of ongoing investigations but experimental evidence suggests that it is lower than the currently assumed 0.4. Note also that EN 1996 [9] only states that "the shear modulus, G , may be taken as 40 % of the elastic modulus, E ." Adapting therefore a lower ratio is therefore not in contradiction with the rules of EN 1996.

4.2 Ratio of effective to initial stiffness

2004	9.4(3)	(3) In the absence of an accurate evaluation of the stiffness properties, substantiated by rational analysis, the cracked bending and shear stiffness may be taken as one half of the gross section uncracked elastic stiffness.
2018		Delete since redundant with 7.3.1.3(3)EC8

The effective stiffness of unreinforced masonry walls subjected to horizontal loading is still a topic of research [12]. Experimental results on modern URM walls show that both the initial and the effective stiffness seem to increase with the axial load ratio (ALR) [12]. They can be written as an initial stiffness that is a function of the ALR and an effective to initial stiffness ratio that is constant [12]. For modern URM walls, the mean ratio of the effective to initial stiffness ratio is closer to 0.75 than to 0.50 [12] while for stone masonry walls the effective to initial stiffness ratio is close to 0.50 [13]. For both types of masonry walls, the scatter of the ratios of effective to initial stiffness is, however, very significant-

The prEN1998-1-1 [11] suggests to use an effective to initial stiffness ratio of 0.50 for reinforced concrete and masonry elements (Section 7.3.1.3(3)). This ratio is applied to both the flexural and the shear stiffness. Because the study in [12] does not comprise all masonry typologies nor reinforced or confined masonry, it is suggested to maintain the ratio of 0.50 for masonry piers although recent studies suggest that for unreinforced masonry more accurate evaluations of the stiffness properties can be obtained as follows:

- The E -modulus should be a function of the ALR; empirical relationships for hollow clay brick and calcium silicate brick masonry are given in [12];
- The effective to initial stiffness ratio is approximately 0.75.

Spandrels are generally subjected to low normal forces. In particular for unreinforced masonry, the effective stiffness is a function of the normal force acting on the member. For this reason it is recommended to use a lower ratio of cracked to uncracked member stiffness for spandrels than for piers.

Section 7.3.1.3 in EC8-Part 1 [11]:

7.3.1.3 Stiffness

(1) The stiffness of secondary seismic elements against seismic actions should be neglected. However, when the total contribution to lateral stiffness of all lateral-force resisting secondary seismic elements exceeds 15% of that of the primary lateral-force resisting system, a complementary seismic analysis with a model including all lateral-force resisting secondary elements should be performed and the more unfavourable seismic actions resulting from both analyses should be considered in the verification of the primary seismic elements ~~resulting from both analyses should be considered for verification.~~

(2) In concrete buildings, in composite steel-concrete buildings and in masonry buildings the stiffness of the concrete and masonry primary seismic elements should be evaluated considering the effect of cracking. For concrete buildings elements and composite steel-concrete buildings elements, this effect corresponds to the initiation of yielding of the reinforcement.

(3) Unless a more accurate analysis of the cracked elements is performed, the elastic flexural and shear stiffness properties of concrete and masonry elements according to (2) may be taken to be equal to one-half of the corresponding stiffness of the uncracked elements.

4.3 Redistribution of forces

2004	9.4(6)	(6) The base shear in the various walls, as obtained by the linear analysis described in Section 4, may be redistributed among the walls, provided that: a) the global equilibrium is satisfied (i.e. the same total base shear and position of the force resultant is achieved); b) the shear in any wall is neither reduced more than 25 %, nor increased by more than 33%; and c) the consequences of the redistribution for the diaphragm(s) are taken into account.
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prEN 1996-1 does not give rules for the redistribution of internal forces for unreinforced masonry or confined masonry elements. For reinforced masonry, it gives some rules. However, as I understood it, prEN 1996 contains only rules for the redistribution of forces for RM elements subjected mainly to vertical loading (Section 7.5.3). For elements subjected to in-plane horizontal loading (Section 7.5.6) redistribution rules do not seem to be specified. Does 7.5.3 apply in this case?

The presented approach assumes that the behaviour component factor q_R accounts already for a redistribution of forces. For this reason, the rules for the limitations on the redistribution of forces differentiate between the following cases:

$q_R = 1.0$: Redistribution is allowed within the limits derived by the proposal by Magenes [21]. As a novelty, it links limitations to the redistribution of forces obtained from elastic analysis to the deformation capacity of elements.

$q_R > 1.0$ from tabulated values, URM and CM: A redistribution of forces is already taken account through q_R and conceptually a further redistribution of forces should therefore not be permitted. However, if no redistribution is permitted, often the piers in which the axial load is very low govern the elastic limit of the structure and therefore the seismic design on the basis of behaviour factors. This is outlined in more detail in the following:

- The axial force in piers might be very low as a result of the axial forces from gravity loads or due to coupling effects as a result of the seismic action.

- In unreinforced masonry piers, the shear and flexural capacity are almost proportional to the axial load. As a result, piers with load axial loads tend to be the first ones to reach their force capacity.

To avoid that such walls govern unduly the design, it is suggested to permit a limited redistribution. To ensure that the clause is used to this purpose, the maximum redistribution is limited by a fraction of the total storey force rather than the pier shear force as obtained by elastic analysis. In this way also piers with zero axial load are covered for which the flexural capacity is zero. This approach can be justified as follows:

- The pier stiffness estimates are associated with significant uncertainties.
- The effect of the ALR on the pier stiffness is typically not accounted for. The relative stiffness of piers is therefore in most models not correctly represented. It is therefore questionable to express the limits of the redistribution as a function of the pier shear force, which is highly dependent on the relative pier stiffnesses of one storey.
- Limiting the maximum shear force that can be redistributed as a function of the storey shear force should limit redistributions for large walls, which contribute a significant portion of the storey shear resistance.

The proposed limit is based on a discussion with G. Magenes and P. Morandi (16.5.2019).

$q_R > 1.0$ from tabulated values, RM: The redistribution of forces should be carried out according to prEN 1996-1 7.5.3.5.

q_R from nonlinear analysis: If q_R is derived from nonlinear analysis as $q_R = \alpha_u / \alpha_1$, redistribution of forces is not permitted.

5 Design criteria and construction rules

5.1 Geometric requirements for shear walls

2004		<p>(5) Shear walls should conform to certain geometric requirements, namely:</p> <p>a) the effective thickness of shear walls, t_{ef}, may not be less than a minimum value, $t_{ef,min}$;</p> <p>b) the ratio h_{ef}/t_{ef} of the effective wall height (see EN 1996-1-1:2004) to its effective thickness may not exceed a maximum value, $(h_{ef}/t_{ef})_{max}$; and</p> <p>c) the ratio of the length of the wall, l, to the greater clear height, h, of the openings adjacent to the wall, may not be less than a minimum value, $(l/h)_{min}$.</p> <p>NOTE The values ascribed to $t_{ef,min}$, $(h_{ef}/t_{ef})_{max}$ and $(l/h)_{min}$, for use in a country may be found in its National Annex of this document. The recommended values of $t_{ef,min}$, $(h_{ef}/t_{ef})_{max}$ and $(l/h)_{min}$ are listed in Table 9.2.</p>
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Table 9.2: Recommended geometric requirements for shear walls			
Masonry type	$t_{ef,min}$ (mm)	$(h_{ef}/t_{ef})_{max}$	$(l/h)_{min}$
Unreinforced, with natural stone units	350	9	0,5
Unreinforced, with any other type of units	240	12	0,4
Unreinforced, with any other type of units, in cases of low seismicity	170	15	0,35
Confined masonry	240	15	0,3
Reinforced masonry	240	15	No restriction

Symbols used have the following meaning:

t_{ef} thickness of the wall (see EN 1996-1-1:2004);

h_{ef} effective height of the wall (see EN 1996-1-1:2004);

h greater clear height of the openings adjacent to the wall;

l length of the wall.

(6) Shear walls not conforming to the minimum geometric requirements of (5) of this subclause may be considered as secondary seismic elements. They should conform to 9.5.2(1) and (2).

Effective thickness

It is proposed to remove the limit on the minimum thickness and to replace it by a statement saying that the wall thickness should be chosen to result in a robust behaviour and that the wall thickness should satisfy the outcome of the calculations to this standard.

This approach follows the approach taken in EC6, both in the new version (10.1.2 of [9]) and current version (8.1.2 of [22]). Note that both versions also include the possibility of fixing the minimum wall thickness as NDP. It seems therefore not necessary to include the effective thickness again as an NDP in EC8-1-2.

A minimum effective thickness could be derived using the following approaches:

- Rocking of bodies is size dependent. Therefore not only the slenderness ratio but also the size of the element (here the thickness) could be derived from first principles.
- The effective boundary conditions of walls are dependent on the wall thickness, slab stiffnesses, connection details between walls and slab and construction tolerances.

Slenderness ratios h_{ef}/t_{ef}

See separate background document [23].

Ratio of wall length to wall height l/h

Reasonable wall length to wall height ratios should result from the design process. Prescribing minimum ratios of wall length to wall height might be introduced for the following reasons:

- Second line of defense:
 - Longer wall lengths will result in a stiffer building response and therefore in smaller displacement demands. However, they are also more likely to fail in shear rather than in flexure.
- Limits of empirical studies:
 - The deformation capacity and the q-factors are based on the analyses of limited data sets (deformation capacity: database of quasi-static cyclic wall tests; q-

factors: analyses of reference buildings). It seems therefore opportune to limit the application of this standard to buildings that are within the range of these experimental and numerical studies. Note that these are only available for unreinforced masonry buildings. Equivalent studies for confined or reinforced masonry are not known to the author.

Distribution of l/h for experimental database

Figure 2 shows the wall height to length ratio for walls in the European database [24] with a height equal to or larger than 1.5 m [10]. The current version of EC8-Part 1 [25] prescribes a minimum wall length to wall height ratio of 0.40 and 0.35 for low and moderate-high seismicity, respectively. This corresponds to a maximum h/l ratio of 2.5 and 2.9 respectively. Figure 2 shows that only for two types of units (HC and CS) such slender walls were tested. This could justify that walls with such slenderness ratios should be avoided. On the other hand, such slender walls are likely to fail in flexure and carry a relatively small shear force; they are therefore unlikely to control the overall deformation capacity of the building.

Figure 2: Dataset after applying the height limit of 1.5 m [10]: Slenderness ratio of walls as a function of the unit type. HC = hollow clay units, SB = solid units, CS = calcium silicate units, AAC = Autoclaved aerated concrete units, LAC = Light-weight aerated concrete units.

Distribution of wall length to wall height ratios in analysed building configurations

The proposed behaviour factors are based on work Paolo Morandi, Guido Magenes and their masonry research group in Pavia [26]–[29] and the research group by Christoph Butenweg in Aachen [30]–[32], see background document on behaviour factors. Both works are based on the analyses of representative building configurations. Figure 3 shows the distribution of wall height to storey height for each of the analysed building configurations. The storey height was assumed as 2.80 m for both studies. It shows that most walls of the case study buildings were longer than 0.4 times the storey height. None of the analysed buildings had only walls that were shorter than 0.4 times the storey height.

Figure 3: Wall slenderness distribution. Each colour represents one building configuration; each line style one building direction. The thick black line represents a wall length to storey height ratio of 0.4.

File register:

Fig_distr_H_div_L_1.m	Figure 2a
Fig_distr_H_div_L_2.m	Figure 2b
Fig_Morandi_wall_slenderness_distr_001.m	Figure 3a
Fig_Butenweg_wall_slenderness_distr_001.m	Figure 3b

6 Definition of drifts

Added to the document on March 14, 2021

I agree with SL's observation that the drift equation in EC8-1 is independent of the shear span and therefore yields the same value for single- and double-bending. I therefore also agree with the observation that this can be conservative for walls failing in shear when the wall is subjected to single bending (see also Petry and Beyer, 2015). The reasons that this definition was chosen for EC8-1 are the following:

- The drift definition in EC8-1 is consistent with the drift definition adopted for the evaluation of the experimental tests (Beyer et al, 2020).
- Reevaluating the drift capacity of experimental wall tests according to Eq. 11.13 in EC8-3 is difficult because for almost none of the cantilever tests reported in the literature, the top rotation was recorded.
- The drift definition adopted in EC8-3 for elements failing in flexure is similar to the one in EC8-1, only that in EC8-3 the correct definition of the chord rotation is adopted (EC8-3: with regard to contraflexure point; EC8-1: rotation of chord line that joins the two end sections). This simplification was adopted in EC8-1 for the following reasons:
 - For almost all wall tests, the displacement at the contraflexure point is only measured, if the wall is subjected to single bending. In this case, the definitions yield the same result. Re-evaluating the flexural capacity according to Eq. 11.23 and 24 in EC8-3 is therefore difficult.
 - Extracting the displacement at the point of contraflexure might also be difficult for some numerical models (e.g. macro-element models) though here solutions could certainly be implemented.

Figure 1 in PB15 shows that the definition of Eq. 11.13 leads to approximately similar failure drifts for various shear spans. It could therefore be an alternative to the definitions used in Beyer et al., 2020, which accounts for the influence of the shear span on the drift capacity.

References:

Petry S, Beyer K (2015) Limit states of URM piers subjected to seismic in-plane loading, invited publication, *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering* 13(4): 1073-1095. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10518-014-9695-9>, extract at the end of this document

Beyer K, Wilding B, Rezaie A (2020) Drift capacity models for modern URM walls, Background document for the masonry chapter in EC8 Part 1, Technical report, Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, Switzerland. <https://zenodo.org/record/2536829>

Working draft

(6) Once the shear V_R is obtained as the minimum among the possible failure modes, the piecewise linear force-deformation relationship should be defined in terms of shear force and drift ratio for the three relevant damage levels, defined in 11.3.2.1(4). Element drift ratio θ_e should be defined as given by Formula (11.13).

$$\theta_e = \frac{u_j - u_i}{h} + \frac{r_j + r_i}{2} \quad (11.13)$$

where:

$u_{i(j)}$ is the lateral displacement at the end section $i(j)$;

h is the length of the masonry element (pier or spandrel);

$r_{i(j)}$ is the rotation at the end section $i(j)$, assumed positive if counter-clockwise, when $(u_j - u_i)/h$ is positive clock-wise.

11.4.1.2.2 Elements failing in flexure

(1) The ultimate displacement capacity of an unreinforced masonry pier controlled by flexure should be expressed in terms of the drift at which the chord rotation θ_{ij} at the lower i end section (or upper j end section) where the flexural resistance corresponding to $\theta_{i,c} = 0,01(1-\nu)$ is attained, where ν is the normalised axial load defined in 11.4.1.1.2(2). The chord rotation should be taken as given by Formulas (11.23) and (11.24).

$$\theta_i = r_i + \frac{u_0 - u_i}{H_i} \quad (11.23)$$

$$\theta_j = r_j + \frac{u_j - u_0}{H_j} \quad (11.24)$$

$$\theta_i = r_i + \frac{u_j - u_i}{H}, \theta_j = r_j + \frac{u_j - u_i}{H}$$

where:

u_0 is the transversal displacement at the contraflexure point;

$r_{i(j)}$ is the rotation at the lower(upper) end section $i(j)$, assumed as positive counter-clockwise, when $u_j - u_i$, $u_j - u_0$, $u_0 - u_i$ are positive clock-wise;

$H_{i(j)}$ is the distance between the section $i(j)$ and the contraflexure point ($H_i + H_j = H$, where H is the height of the pier).

Commenté [36]:

Commenté [PF37]: Don't understand. Replicated formulas?

Commenté [PB38R37]: SL: 11.4.1.2.2(1) - Eqns. (11.23) and (11.24) consider explicitly u_0 because the displacement is aligned with those at the i and j sections only when the contraflexure point is in the middle of the beam. However, the simplified formulas, suggested in the comment, give acceptable results in all cases and are compatible with the definition of element drift ratio (11.13) in 11.4.1.1(6), recalled in 11.4.1.2.2(1).

Extracts from Draft of EC8-Part 1

14.9. Ultimate deformations

14.9.1. General

(1) The drift ratio or chord rotation θ_e of a masonry member should be calculated as given by Formula (14.18).

$$\theta_e = \max(\theta_i, \theta_j) \quad (14.18)$$

where θ_i (resp. θ_j) is the angle between the member axis at end section i (respectively j) and the chord line that joins the centroids of the two end sections.

14.9.2. Unreinforced masonry members

(1) $\theta_{2,50}$ of piers failing in shear should be taken as a) or b):

Commenté [PB55]: SL: This definition of the drift is fine in the case of flexural failure mechanisms, that occur at the end section, but is very demanding for shear failure mechanism. Indeed, it provides the same value of the drift in the case of a cantilever or of a beam with fixed rotation at both ends, subjected to the same transversal displacement: it is well known that shear deformation (and shear force) in the first case is less demanding. More accurate definitions are provided in EN1998-3: eqn. (11.13) in 11.4.1.1(6) for shear; eqns. (11.23) and (11.24) in 11.4.1.2.2(1) for flexure.

Limit states of modern unreinforced clay brick masonry walls subjected to in-plane loading

S. Petry · K. Beyer

Fig. 1 Force-drift envelopes obtained with the chord rotation θ_{CR} , the interstorey drift δ_H and the drift measure θ_{Lag+13} proposed by Lagomarsino et al. (2013)

Fig. 2 Definition of the chord rotation for shear spans $H_0 < H$ and $H_0 > H$

of chord rotation, see Fig. 2. When subjected to cantilever or fixed-fixed boundary conditions, interstorey drift and chord rotation are per definition equal (note that, strictly speaking, this assumption does not hold for fixed-fixed boundary conditions if the damage to the top and base of the wall is not identical). Since wall tests reported in the literature applied either of the two boundary conditions, the difference between interstorey drift and chord rotation had not been investigated. The EPFL campaign comprised tests with $H_0/H = 0.75$ and 1.5 and therefore the difference between chord rotation and interstorey drift is of interest. In addition, the drift measure proposed by Lagomarsino et al. (2013) is compared to the interstorey drift and the chord rotation. This drift measure is based on the assumption that the in-plane shear deformation is a better indicator of the wall damage and was originally proposed for the structural member's drift, although in some cases it may coincide with the interstorey drift (Penna, personal communication, Oct. 2014).

The interstorey drift (short: drift) is the total lateral displacement at the top of the wall divided by the storey height (in our case the storey height is equal to the height of the wall H):

$$\delta_H = \frac{u_H}{H} \quad (1)$$

where u_H is the relative horizontal displacement between the top and base of the storey-high wall.

The drift measure proposed by Lagomarsino et al. (2013), which is used to determine the limit states of the bi-linear element in Tremuri, subtracts from the interstorey drift the average rotation at the top and base of the wall:

$$\theta_{Lag+13} = \frac{u_H}{H} - \frac{\theta_{top} + \theta_{base}}{2} \quad (2)$$

where θ_{top} and θ_{base} are the rotation at top and base of the wall respectively. Note that the sign convention is such that (i) θ_{top} is positive if the rotation at the top has the same orientation as the rotation at the top of a cantilever wall subjected to a horizontal load leading to a positive displacement u_H , (ii) θ_{base} is positive in the same sense as the top rotation.

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